

SOVIET AND POST-SOVIET HERITAGE OF THE SOCIAL ADVERTISEMENT**Soso Gazdeliani***Ph. D. Student of Mass Communication Doctoral Educational Program
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1 Ilia Tchavtchavadze Avenue, 0179 Tbilisi, Georgia***Abstract**

Initial period of development of the social advertisement exactly coincides with the sovietization of Georgia. The state represented Union of Soviet Socialistic Republics for seventy years.

The present research was conducted using a method of content analysis and historic analyzes and originated qualitatively essential trends. As a matter of curiosity, answers had to be given on the questions: What kind of experience existed in the post-Soviet Georgia from the viewpoint of the social advertisement and what was the impact of the Soviet hand-writing on it?

In the social posters of the Soviet Union an important influence of the hypodermic needle (magic bullet) theory is observed. Social messages of that period directly and rudely intervened into the consciousness of a Soviet citizen and dictated to him how he had to live according to the Soviet values. Messages of the social advertisement often took a face of slogans.

Soviet Heritage in Georgia in this direction left its trace as well. Soviet hand-writing is definitely seen in social advertisements of the Post-Soviet Period.

Keywords: Social Advertisement, Soviet Union, Georgia.

Introduction

Social advertisement is a post-social project of the past century, which that time, on the initial stage, reflected its ideas in the form of posters.

In the Soviet social advertisements, a hypodermic needle (magic bullet) theory had a great importance. The stated theory of the linear communication, without any contexts, was characterized with direct messages, it was targeted at making a strong impact on the human consciousness which is resulted in fulfillment of dictated actions by the society. The stated approach was a kind of hand-writing of the Soviet social posters, and thus, the hypothesis developed by is not groundless.

There is a trivial opinion that in the period of the Soviet totalism advertisement served to the state force. The Government totally controlled the advertising activity. The result was relevant: a majority of social posters often contained ideological and political context.

Our aim is to determine/ to detect/ to define the contextual features and key discoveries of the social advertisements/ posters created in the Soviet and Post-Soviet period.

For reaching of the target, we determined the following tasks: using the method of content analysis we reviewed a content of social posters/ advertisement, forms and means of expression in the Soviet and Post-Soviet period.

Methodology

The research, particularly, was carried using the method of qualitative research. Based on the historic analysis and content analysis we investigated historic pre-conditions and content-related aspects of the social advertisements.

The content analysis is focused on importance of the context. It assists us in detailed analyzing of what

the studied material represents. On top of all, results received by the stated method may be checked.

The method of content-analysis essentially helped us in studying of the content of Soviet/ Post-Soviet social posters and revealing of key trends.

In the present research the historic angle of aspect is a key direction. Accordingly, we could not overpass the qualitative research as well as the actual and important method in the field of social science – historic analysis. With its support we reviewed old forms / examples of the advertising activity and pro-social activism. A method of historic analysis enables us to see the whole image of the process and to determine the newest trends based on the old experience.

Theoretic frame

The hypodermic needle theory, or as it is called in other way, of magic bullet theory represents one of the theoretic bases of the subject being under research. We may say that it is a fundamental theory of mass communication in which we talk about the speed of information circulation and the effect of reflux obtaining of media messages by a recipient. As a rule, the theory of linear communication has a direct and strong effect on the audience. In simple words, human beings believe in the content reported by the media outlets.

The theory was created in 20-30s of the past century after the researchers had fixed the propaganda's effect during the First World War. During the next decades a model of the hypodermic needle transformed into a dominated theory about media impact.

Michael Salwen and Don Stacks in their book "Integrated approach in the communication theory and research" write: "A model of the subcutaneous needle was dominant till 1940" (Stacks, Salwen & Eichhorn, 2019), - despite of the fact that the hypodermic needle theory was rejected by a part of theoreticians it will be

constantly actual simultaneously with the media's impact on the society.

Critics of the hypodermic needle theory name several reasons of its rejecting, mainly: a) the theory neglects the audience's role in the process of interpretation of media messages and responding on them; b) the theory allows the opinion that media has a one-sided impact on the audience; c) the theory lightly observes the process of communication and media effects; d) the theory is based on hypotheses about nature of human beings and not on results of the empiric research (Gabunia, Reviewed, & Drew, 2023).

Under the hypodermic needle theory, media messages look like subcutaneous needles (Berger, 1995), which provide passive recipients with ideas, values and belief. Media messages similarly with the injection rapidly intervene into the human consciousness, and thus their impact is efficient and instantaneous.

Examples of the subcutaneous needle theory include: applying of the direct advertising, influence of the social media, posting of products and their approving by famous people for the purpose of rapid effecting on social behavior.

Under the Hypodermic Needle Theory, media messages are powerful and able to form social opinion and behavior. If the TV advertisement demonstrates a product as a solution of a definite problem, the theory supposes that the audience will be assured in its efficiency immediately (Magic Bullet Theory).

Society is not able to avoid the media impact and thus it is compared with the "Sitting Goose" (Croteau & Hoynes, 1997). The socius is always sensitive towards the messages specially delivered to it.

The second name – "Magic Bullet Theory" considers media as a weapon, and its message, as a bullet which is shoot purposefully to recipients. Under the theory, the stated attitude is necessary for mobilization of the passive audience.

The theory proves that creators of media content are able to manipulate with the targeted audience and to determine recipient's behavior significantly in a simple way.

The Hypodermic Needle Theory shows practical results in social advertising, particularly in almost all social posters created in the post-Soviet period.

Dominating of the theory coincides with the Soviet period, accordingly, creators of social posters probably used the effect of the "Magic Bullet" to make a direct impact on the Soviet citizens; all this is proved by the slogans of that period.

In the period of the Soviet totalism, advertisement was serving to the state force. The government fully controlled the advertising activity. The target of the Government was to form an absolutely new, devoted to the Party society having special values which, in their opinion, should overcome a lack of education and to implement useful ideas about communism.

In the Soviet period social advertisements in the form of messages were characterized with a special activity which, surely, served to the Government.

At first glance the extent of impulsivity of the Soviet totalitarian "Social Advertisement" is vivid. It is direct and is easily and roughly interfering into the conscience of the Soviet citizens. The soviet social posters

contain direct messages/ likes, it dictates to the society how it should behave. It is a clear example of the open propaganda which is approached to the above-mentioned theoretic concept. Social advertisements of the Soviet Union provide us with an opportunity of supposition and expression of a definite hypothesis.

Hypothesis

H₁: Significant effect of the Hypodermic Needle/Magic Bullet Theory is observed in the social advertisements/ posters of the Soviet Union.

Discussion and results

In several days after the Revolution of 1917 a Decree "About implementation of the state monopoly on the advertisement" signed by Lenin was issued. Information monopoly was created and social advertisement became a product of politics; due to this fact their unbundling became very difficult. By using of social messages, the government systematically taught the society to think that the new governing regime is natural and constant; Soviet and Non-Soviet World existed.

Authorized and popular heroes were actively used in the social advertisement of the Soviet period. One of them Vladimir Mayakovsky who left a significant advertising heritage. He is an author of many rhythmic advertising slogans.

At a glance, even insignificant advertisements of the Soviet period reflect political sub-text. For instance, a slogan of the "advertisement on galoshes" was as follows: "**Europe may sit and cry without galoshes**".

In the Soviet Union, and, generally, all over the world, new means of communication are appearing gradually; in 90s of the past century almost all families had radio transmitters. After 1950s an instrument of innovative communication – TV-set appeared. Initially, its impact on the society was insignificant as TV-set was a rare event. Sometimes later, in parallel with rising of its availability, this communication channel became the most efficient mean of transmitting of information. Social advertisement via TV was represented by means of educational programs reporting advantages of the Soviet life.

The Soviet governing force had the following task: to form an absolutely new, devoted to the Party society having specific values, which, in their opinion should overcome a lack of education and to implement useful ideas about communism. For instance, in one of the Soviet posters there was Vladimir Lenin against the background of the sun. It had a legend "**Labor will be the world's sovereign**". Here, we may conclude that the "World's Sovereign" was associated with the Revolution Leader. Here, we should remind a post demonstrating people with positive emotions, against their background we see the following legend: "Communist Party". Next to it there is an avocation "**Enter the Communist Party**". Idea of the poster is easily recognizable, - as if entering the Communist Party brings happiness and gladness.

In the Soviet period social advertisements existed in the form of messages which in any case supported the government and contained a political context. One of such messages was as follows: "**The October Revolution is a bridge to the bright future**". Obviously, it was one of the expressions of manipulative activities to demonstrate to the Soviet people how important are

changes in the society. "Better" changes would be only connected with communism.

On the another poster which had a similar ideological context the following leaders are imaged: Marks, Engels, Lenin, Stalin and a train. We can read a message on it: "**The train is going from the Socialism station – to Communism Station**".

From the first sight we can clearly see the extent of impulsivity of the Soviet totalitarian advertisement, which fully serves to popularization of the power. It is direct and is easily and harshly intervening into the life of Soviet citizens. We can consider it as another one key indicator which strengthen our hypothesis in connection with the effect of the Hypodermic Needle Theory.

From 50s of the past century the Soviet government slightly weakened its influence on the advertisement. It is a sufficient precondition for enabling of the advertisement to show not only the government's, but the social interests as well. All this became a definite trigger for creation of a truly social advertisement in the Social reality.

On the initial stage social advertisements focused on popularization of healthy life style became very active. In 1930s anti-tobacco advertisement appeared. In the Soviet 30s too many posters were created and they were directed against tobacco consumption. Here are legends printed on them: "**Nicotine is a poison**", "**Our ultimatum to the senior generation**", "**Here, smoking is banned, but I am smoking**", "**Smoking tobacco is expensive and harmful for one's health and owner**". Content of the posters was improving gradually from the visual and content-related viewpoint.

In the Soviet Union, on top of the above-mentioned harmful habit, social campaign directed against alcohol consumption was conducted actively. On one of the Soviet poster, we can read the following legend: "**What can children buy at the cost of one liter of vodka**". On the poster a bottle of vodka is crossed and all the products useful for children are represented around.

The Soviet social advertisement was packaged with the song as well. The easily remembered composition was adapted easily with the films popular that time: "**Girls**", "**Height**" and others. Here we face the advertisements about the routine life of Soviet citizens, its character and values.

The Soviet Union was included in the list of the not numerous countries which focused their attention on the social problems such as sexual humiliation and prostitution. The Soviet Union, to eliminate this viciousness, actively created social posters, on one of such posters we can read the following slogan: "**Down the ugly women**". As it is seen, the women involved in prostitution were determined with the epithet of an ugly woman for the Soviet Union.

In the Soviet Union a great attention is paid on the traffic safety. In 1930s the first slogan calling for following of traffic rules appeared: "**Breaching of rules pose your life under threat**".

Following of hygienic norms in the Soviet period also was a subject of significant concern. Since the year of 1931 the public sector actively started calling for following of hygiene which considered a direct instruction

and sounded as follows: 'Wash your hands before work and taking a meal'.

The Soviet Union, by means of the social posters, actively promoted development of physical culture and sport by means of social posters, that is confirmed by the posters created in 1947 with the following slogans: "**Young people go to the stadium!**" and "**Work, build and do not ccomplain**".

In the Soviet Period, for supporting of the tourism, social campaigns were carried actively. We would like to remind you that in that period travelling across the borders of the Soviet Union was very difficult. Thus, internal tourism was very popular and Soviet posters mainly served to its development/ promoting. Slogans of several posters were read as follows: "**On the day-off a touristic tour**" (1947); "**Be a tourist!**" (1949). On top of all, to promote the field of tourism, definite professions were advertised, for instance of a pilot: "**Young people to the airplane**" (1934, G. Klutsis).

In the period of Stalinism majority of Soviet posters, we may say, was devoted not to the party-ideological propaganda, but to the so called "social advertisement". If in the Royal Russia the Church was obliged "to breed the population", in the Soviet Union this role was assigned to the government and scales of the educational work were significantly increased: there was a need for formation of consciousness of "a new human being", a new life style to overcome lack of education and others.

One of the tasks of the Soviet regime was releasing of a woman, emancipation, her transformation into an active builder of the new society. Relevant posters existed and they had a direct and slightly imperative tone, for instance: "**Woman, do study reading**"; it is the poster, as it is seen in the slogan/calling, struggling against a lack of education among women. Besides, there were posters which were targeted at releasing of women from domestic works and their involving into the public works. The latter one is confirmed by the poster with the following slogan: "**Down the kitchen slavery**".

In the Soviet social advertisement, a key role was assigned to supporting of representatives of difficult and noble professions. Posters created around this issue had reached our time and are generally devoted to physicians, teachers and church men: "**Respect and Glory to Village Physician**"; "**Glory to the Priest**"; "**Glory to the Teacher!**".

In the period of Stalinism one of the most ambitious projects was the so called "**Cultural Revolution**", which, as it was mentioned before, was targeted at fully eliminating of the lack of education, opening of libraries, clubs, cinemas, new schools and institutes. Social posters of the same period are accented, majorly, on the values and advantages, such as family purity and its respect: "**Respect to family**".

After collapsing of the Soviet Union, since the year of 1991 a process of decentralization and struggling of the republics for independence was launched. The republics had to stay in totalitarian pliers for decades. By the date of obtaining of independence, Georgia had only one state television and several independent printed publication houses.

Upon starting of the post-totalitarian period, since the year of 1992 – in terms of politically very difficult, but revived commercial relations, a demand for advertisement appeared in Georgia. That time the **State TeleRadioCommittee** was still broadcasting and under its subordination the **Second TV-Channel** was founded.

Since 1992 broadcasting of the first advertisement was started in Georgia. That time advertisements were prepared by the television edition team and attached titers to images.

For technical supporting of advertisements only one advertisement agency “**TV Advertisement TV+**” existed. Besides, since the years of 1992-93 Clipping room “**Betacam**” was opened in the newly built Hotel “**Metekhi**” which also was preparing TV advertisements. By 1992, television was recognized as the most popular environment for placing of advertisements (Peradze, Marketing Communication – History of Advertisement, 2010, page 299).

Since 1994, products of foreign companies, such as: **Wrigley, Dirol, Ferrero, Proctor & Gamble** and others entered the Georgian advertising market.

Since 1994, when a new TV Channel “**Rustavi 2**” was created, it became a serious competitor to the monopolistic Teleradiocorporation (the recent “**First Channel**”) which that time had been occupying the largest share of the advertising market.

Opening of the branch of “**Coca Cola**” in Georgia is recognized as a gradual change of development of Georgian advertising, as well as appearing of “**Geocell**” and “**Magti**” on the TV space.

Advertisements of the post-totalitarian period, practically were doubling the foreign ones. Simple graphic and animated advertising clips were majorly met on air. Competition existing between “**Geocell**” and “**Magti**” actually triggered preparation of the original and power advertisement (Peradze, Marketing Communication – History of advertisement, 2010, page 300).

By the end of the past century a large part of the advertising market was kept by the beer companies “**Kazbegi**” and “**Castel**”. Significant time was devoted to advertising of the products of pharmaceutical products.

Since 1995, from the viewpoint of placing of advertisements, after TV, the largest part was occupied by the external advertising. As for radio and printed publication houses, in the first decade of the Post-totalitarian epoch, they were deemed as less popular means of advertising.

Distribution of the advertising market in the 21st century was continued. Moreover, in the current century a number of media outlets was increased that is in direct proportion with increasing of the number of advertisements. In terms of competition between the media market and advertising agencies advertisement is being improved gradually.

Social advertisements in the first decade of the Post-soviet period may be deemed as rather weak. It is remarkable that technical opportunities existing that time did not provide a basis for creation of complete social clips.

Social advertisements created in the period since 1991 – till the beginning of the 21st century were generally devoted to collecting of donations, timely conducting of vaccination against different diseases, awakening of patriotic moods, taking care of old districts of

the city. Themes and slogans were looked like as follows (1991-2000): “April 15-22 are the day of donations”; “Take your family to vaccination! From 3 – to 60 years old”; “We will return”; “Take care over the old Tbilisi”; “Remember...”.

Conclusion

Historic analysis and content analyses of the Soviet Social posters provided us with the opportunity of detecting of key trends and despecification of results: primarily, it is noteworthy that the Soviet government was characterized with direct messages which is vividly observed in slogans and messages of social posters. This fact supports hypothesis that for the purpose of receiving of a strong effect Soviet posters were created based on the hypodermic needle theory, in which key moments of the linear concept were thoroughly considered.

The Soviet advertisement used to be a kind of bridge between the government and people. It was characterized with the following adjectives: bright, colorful, loud, clear slogans and others. It attracted attention of Soviet citizens and probably a degree of its impact was too high.

We may divide the social advertisement in two categories: advertisements containing political-ideological context which could not express the past reality; moreover, it was too far from genuine routine and purely prosocial posters which referred to different social problems and challenges and ways of their solving.

In fact, we can say that a large part of social advertisements of the Soviet period reported not about the way of living of a soviet people, but how they had to live according to the Soviet values.

Proceeding from general characteristic features of the Soviet social advertisements we may confirm a hypothesis expressed by us according to which a significant impact of the hypodermic needle/ magic bullet theory on the social posters is remarkable.

In the first decade of the post-totalitarian period, means of audiovisual imaging, naturally, could not suggest the best quality for that time, narration was minimalistic and slightly primitive, but sometimes later, simultaneously with the technological progress, social advertisement takes contently and technically improved forms that is one of the key pre-conditions for reaching of its targets.

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